

Protease Activity of Rabbit Brain Tissue

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The complete spectrum of protease activity of rabbit brain homogenate was not revealed by traditional protease substrates, haemoglobin and casein. Whereas, these two substrates sufficed for detecting protease activity at acidic and alkaline pHs, azocasein, a chromogenic substrate was needed to demonstrate an important protease activity peak at slightly acidic pH values. The brain homogenate contains protease activity over the entire pH range from 2.0-10.0 with peaks of activity around pH 3.5, 5.0 and 8.5. Pepstatin, a specific inhibitor of cathepsin D was utilised to show that almost entire protease activity in peak I was due to this protease. That the second peak consisted of cathepsin B and BANA-hydrolase was shown by using BANA as substrate and leupeptin as inhibitor. Leupeptin, a specific inhibitor for cathepsin B could not completely abolish the BANA-hydrolase activity at 1.0 μ M concentration sufficient to completely inhibit the activity of pure cathepsin B. Further, Z-L-Arg-L-Arg 4m β NA, a highly specific chromogenic substrate for cathepsin B was utilised for the first time to demonstrate the presence of cathepsin B in rabbit brain. At 1.0 μ M concentration of leupeptin, the complete inhibition of Z-Arg-Arg-4m β NA activity confirms the presence of cathepsin B.

SMALL bio-active peptides are present in the central nervous system. They act as neurotransmitters and regulators of hormonal activity. The control mechanism for these neuropeptides, i.e. their formation and inactivation has generated tremendous interest in the field of neurochemistry but evaded proper understanding as yet. In a recent review, Marks¹ has highlighted the involvement of brain proteases *vis-à-vis* these biopeptides. Most of the work in the area of brain proteases has been done on acid-acting hydrolase²⁻⁴, cathepsin D (EC 3.4.23.5) and some neutral and alkaline proteases^{5,6}. In our overall programme of identifying peptide hydrolases present in the central nervous system, we had reported earlier⁷ that the brain tissue contains proteases active over the entire pH range from 2.5 to 10.5. The most prominent peak was, however, at pH 3.5-4.0 which was shown by the use of a specific inhibitor pepstatin, to be entirely due to cathepsin D. In the light of the fact that a very strong peak of activity comprising protein-hydrolysing enzymes active at slightly acidic pH values has been reported from other tissues^{8,9}, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the presence of such proteinases in brain. In the present study, we report the use of a chromogenic substrate, azocasein, in addition to haemoglobin and casein to detect the proteases active over entire pH range. This substrate made possible a new peak of protease activity at slightly acidic pH values (not detected by haemoglobin and casein). By using a new and highly specific substrate, Z-Arg-Arg-4m β NA for cathepsin B (EC 3.4.22.1), coupled with its specific inhibitor leupeptin, the presence of cathepsin B and a separate enzyme, BANA-hydrolase is reported.

Experimental

Rabbit brain acetone powder which was used as the source of brain tissue homogenate was purchased

from Pel-Freeze Biological Inc. Rogers, (U. S. A.). Haemoglobin, azocasein, dithioerythritol (DTE), α -N-benzoyl-D,L-arginine- β -naphthylamide (BANA), bovine serum albumin (BSA), *p*-chloromercuribenzoic acid (PCMB), Fast Garnet GBC dye were purchased from Sigma Chemical Co. (U. S. A.). Leupeptin was procured from Peptide Institute Inc. (Japan). α -N-Benzoyloxycarbonyl-L-arginine-L-arginine-4-methoxy- β -naphthylamide (Z-Arg-Arg-4m β -NA) was procured from Enzyme System Products (U.S.A.). All other chemicals used were of highest grade available. Absorption in the uv/visible range was measured on Shimadzu-140-02 (200-1000 nm range) and EC spectrophotometer (350-900 nm range).

Preparation of enzyme homogenate: The rabbit brain acetone powder (10 g) after being stirred for 1 h at 4° in 100 ml of 50 mM sodium acetate buffer pH 5.5 containing 0.2 M NaCl, was homogenised thrice for a period of 15 sec each time in an Osterizer blender. Protein estimation was done according to the method of Lowery *et al*¹⁰.

Assay for proteolytic activity: The protease activity of brain homogenate was estimated at various pHs, with haemoglobin, azocasein and casein as substrates. Haemoglobin substrate was prepared by dialysing a 4% aqueous solution of bovine Hb against several changes of ion-free distilled water for 48 h. Azocasein substrate was prepared by dialysing azocasein solution (in 0.1 N NaOH) against water for 48 h. The dialysed azocasein was adjusted to pH 6.0 and was made 4%. Casein substrate was prepared by dissolving 4 g casein in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.5. The 4% substrates prepared above were diluted to 1 : 1 with 0.2 M buffers of appropriate pHs for protease assay. 1.0 ml of this resultant 2% substrate in 0.1 M buffer was incubated with 1.0 ml of brain homogenate at 40°

for 3 h. The reaction was stopped by the addition of 3.0 ml of 5% TCA and the precipitated material was filtered off after centrifugation on a table-top centrifuge. Blanks were also prepared where enzyme homogenate was added after the addition of TCA. The activity was measured quantitatively from the filtrate either by measuring absorbance at 280 nm or colorimetrically as described earlier¹¹.

Assay for BANA-hydrolase activity: BANA-hydrolase activity at various pHs was estimated with BANA as substrate: To 1.5 ml of 0.1 M buffers of various pHs 0.1 ml each of 40 mM EDTA and 40 mM DTE were added. After adding 0.2 ml enzyme homogenate, the final pHs of various samples were recorded as, 2.74, 3.45, 4.12, 4.46, 5.07, 5.78, 5.84, 6.2, 6.96, 7.35, 7.8 and 8.7. The reaction was started by the addition of 0.1 ml of BANA stock solution (40 mg/ml in DMSO) and the incubation carried at 40°. After 1 h, the reaction was stopped by the addition of 2.0 ml of coupling reagent. Blanks were included where enzyme was added after the addition of coupling reagent. After allowing 20 min for colour development, the red colour was extracted into 4.0 ml of n-butanol and estimated by measuring absorbance at 520 nm. The activity of BANA hydrolase is expressed in nanomole of β -naphthylamine liberated/h/ml enzyme. The molar extinction coefficient of β -naphthylamine at 520 nm, under the present assay conditions, was taken as 25000¹¹.

Assay of BANA-hydrolase in presence of leupeptin: Stock solution (0.001M) of leupeptin was prepared by dissolving 1.1 mg leupeptin in 2.5 ml incubation buffer (EDTA/phosphate buffer). To 1.498 ml of assay buffers of different pHs (2.45, 2.96, 4.0, 4.85, 5.34, 5.92, 6.54, 6.93, 8.45 and 9.00) 0.2 ml of enzyme was added followed by 2 μ l of leupeptin solution in assay buffer to affect a final concentration of 1.0 μ M in the assay. After pre-incubation of 10 min, 0.1 ml each of 40 mM EDTA and 40 mM DTE were added. The final pHs of all the test-tubes were recorded as 2.70, 3.09, 4.02, 4.85, 5.32, 5.77, 6.5, 6.85, 7.62 and 8.1. After further incubation of 5 min, 0.1 ml of BANA stock solution was added to start the reaction. Blanks and control assays were also included, where enzyme was added after the addition of coupling reagent in blanks and no leupeptin was added in control experiments. The reaction products were processed as described above.

Assay of cathepsin B with Z-Arg-Arg-4m β NA as substrate: To 1.0 ml of 0.2 M buffers of various pHs (2.17, 2.96, 4.02, 4.90, 5.53, 6.03, 6.52, 7.49 and 8.42), 0.55 ml water was added followed by 0.2 ml enzyme, 0.1 ml each of 40 mM EDTA and 40 mM DTE. The reaction was started by the addition of 50 μ l of Z-Arg-Arg-4m β NA (8 mg/ml DMSO). The final pHs were recorded as 2.90, 3.26, 4.28, 5.0, 5.62, 6.03, 6.58, 7.27 and 7.68. The reaction tubes were incubated at 40° for 1 h before adding 2.0 ml of coupling reagent. Blanks were also included where enzyme was added after the addition of coupling

reagent. Colour was allowed to develop for 20 min after which it was extracted into 4.0 ml of n-butanol and estimated at 520 nm. The unit of activity was expressed in nanomole of 4-methoxy- β -naphthylamine/h/ml enzyme. The molar extinction coefficient of 4-methoxy- β -naphthylamine under present assay conditions was taken as 34900¹².

Assay of cathepsin B with Z-Arg-Arg-4m β NA as substrate in presence of leupeptin: To 1.0 ml of 0.2M buffer of various pHs (2.17, 2.96, 4.02, 4.90, 5.53, 6.03, 6.52, 7.49 and 8.42), 0.548 ml of water was added followed by 2 μ l of leupeptin, 0.2 ml of enzyme, 0.1 ml each of 40 mM DTE and 40 mM EDTA, and finally reaction was started by the addition of 50 μ l of Z-Arg-Arg-4m β NA (8 mg/ml DMSO). The rest of the procedure was exactly same as described above.

Results and Discussion

Assays for protease activity: Assay procedures had to be standardised⁷ due to the large amount of protein present in the crude brain homogenate, capable of influencing the final pHs of the assay mixtures. Accordingly, after mixing the 4% substrate with 0.2M buffers of various pHs, the pH values were adjusted with 1 N HCl or 1 N NaOH to yield the 2% substrates of following pH values, Hb, 1.43, 2.31, 3.55, 4.78, 5.67, 6.41, 7.03, 7.76, 8.48, 9.29 and 11.58; azocasein, 1.18, 1.46, 3.86, 4.74, 5.22, 6.40, 6.93, 7.15, 8.46, 9.83 and 11.46; and casein, 1.25, 1.72, 3.85, 4.50, 4.97, 5.93, 7.59, 8.59, 9.40, 9.63 and 10.23. When 1.0 ml out of these stock substrate solutions was mixed with 1.0 ml of the enzyme homogenate, the resulting pHs were: Hb, 1.50, 2.51, 3.58, 4.98, 5.80, 6.48, 6.95, 7.52, 8.32, 8.77 and 9.50; azocasein, 2.0, 3.37, 4.41, 5.16, 5.68, 6.65, 7.04, 7.06, 8.32, 9.17 and 10.00; and casein, 1.56, 2.90, 4.08, 4.75, 5.10, 6.25, 7.11, 7.45, 7.89, 8.41 and 9.05. The samples were prepared in quadruplicate so that assays were performed in triplicate and the fourth sample tube was utilised to measure the final pH of the assay mixture. The TCA-soluble peptides were quantitated as described above. The azocasein hydrolysing activity was also estimated as absorbance at 366 nm. The activity profiles were the same. Four different experiments done with different enzyme preparations and at different times gave identical results. The results of one typical experiment are shown in Fig. 1. It is abundantly evident that the brain contains proteases active over the entire pH range (2.0-10.0). Both the substrates, Hb and casein, which have traditionally been used for measuring the general protease activity show peaks at acid and alkaline pH values (peaks, Hb at 3.58 and 8.77; casein at 2.90 and 8.41). The peaks with Hb and casein are almost overlapping. These results are in agreement with our earlier work⁷ where Hb and casein were used over limited pH range Hb (2-6), and casein (6-11). The main drawback of using these two substrates becomes

Fig. 1. Protease activity of rabbit brain tissue at different pH values. Buffers used in the pH ranges indicated. Activity expressed as OD₂₈₀ units/h/ml enzyme homogenate at 40°; haemoglobin (○), azocasein (▽), and casein (□).

apparent from the fact that the proteases which are active at slightly acidic pH values are not detected. When azocasein was used as substrate, a strong peak of activity at pH 5.16 highlights the presence of proteases which are active at slightly acidic pH. Barrett⁹ and Singh *et al.*^{1,5} have demonstrated the role of such proteases, present in other tissues, in the degradation of protein substrates.

Identification of proteases present in activity peaks: After demonstrating the presence of proteases in brain tissue active at slightly acidic pH and responsible for the appearance of the third major peak in the activity profile of proteases over the entire pH range, an effort was made to identify the proteases present in the three peaks of Fig. 1. As for the proteases present in first peak (around pH 3.5) we had shown by using a specific inhibitor of cathepsin D that this endopeptidase contributes to a large extent. The inhibitor pepstatin⁶ at a final concentration of 0.1 mM abolished ~90% of the activity in peak I⁷. The proteases from rabbit lung^{1,2,8} and rat liver^{8,9}, which are active at slightly acidic pH and insensitive to pepstatin are cathepsin B, BANA-hydrolase and cathepsin L. The presence of such proteases in central nervous tissue has not yet been reported except for a BANA-hydrolase¹⁴. When the brain homogenate was scanned for BANA-hydrolysing activity over the entire pH range,

maximum activity was obtained between pH 5.5 and 6.0 as shown in Fig. 2. Further characterisation of this BANA-hydrolysing activity was carried out with

Fig. 2. BANA-hydrolysing activity of rabbit brain tissue at various pH values. Activity expressed as nanomole of β -naphthylamine liberated/h/ml enzyme at 40°; activity without leupeptin (○), and activity with leupeptin (▽).

the help of a specific inhibitor of cathepsin B. This inhibitor, leupeptin⁸ (acetyl-L-leucyl-L-leucyl-L-arginal) when incorporated into the assay mixtures at a final concentration of 1 μ M, a concentration sufficient for complete inhibition of purified lung cathepsin B¹⁹ did not completely abolish the BANA-hydrolase activity (~85% inhibition). By analogy with the studies on rabbit lung, the leupeptin-insensitive activity may be due entirely to a new enzyme, BANA-hydrolase.

Activity of cathepsin B: The indication for the presence of cathepsin B in brain as detailed above and also mentioned earlier¹⁴ prompted us to utilise for the first time, a new and highly specific chromogenic substrate for cathepsin B, Z-arg-arg-4m β NA^{1,8} to confirm the activity of this protease in brain tissue. The activity profile is shown in Fig. 3. The complete abolition of this activity by the incorporation of 1 μ M leupeptin concentration demonstrates beyond doubt the presence of cathepsin B in brain and consequently its contribution in the protease peak II of Fig. 1. The presence of the third protease, cathepsin L has not yet been reported from brain tissue. Experiments are in progress in this

Fig. 8. Cathepsin B activity of rabbit brain tissue at various pH values, Z-Arg-Arg-4mβNA as substrate. Enzyme activity expressed as nanomole of 4-methoxy-β-naphthylamine liberated/h/ml enzyme at 40°: activity without leupeptin (○), and activity with leupeptin (▽).

laboratory to identify cathepsin L in brain and also to analyse the proteases present in peak III.

The following conclusion can be interpreted from the experiments carried out on brain tissue with regard to its protease activity. The brain tissue contains proteases active over the entire pH range from pH 2.0 to 10.0. The protease peak at slightly acidic pH values which tends to be masked when traditional substrate Iib and casein are utilised, can be made apparent by using a chromogenic substrate, azocasein. This second peak in the activity profile consists of cathepsin B and a BANAHydrolase, has been proved by using a specific inhibitor and a specific substrate of cathepsin B,

namely leupeptin and Z-Arg-Arg-4mβNA, respectively. The presence of cathepsin L has not yet been reported from brain tissue. The work in this direction is in progress in addition to the work for identification of the third protease peak at alkaline pH values.

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